

Nutritional Evaluation of Local Bread Types in Iraq

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Abstract

The effect of baking conditions (temperature and time) on the nutritional value of five types of local bread was studied using the Trinitrobenzen sulfonic acid (TNBS) chemical method to estimate the percentage of the amino acid lysine in the bread types studied. It was found that the percentages of lysine in French bread, stone bread, laboratory bread, Arabic loaf, tanour bread and microwave bread are 2.718%, 2.430%, 2.538%, 2.853%, 2.510% and 3.102% respectively. It was also found that the percentage of lysine in the crust was less than that in the crumb for all types of bread and that the highest percentage of lysine was in the Arabic bread and the lowest in the stone bread. This was not the case for the microwave loaf, however, which had a percentage of 2.939. The nutritional value of the proteins of these types of bread was also studied by the biological method using laboratory rats (White Albino Rats) by estimating the protein efficiency Ratio (PER) , and it was found that the value of (PER) for the types of bread(French bread, stone bread, laboratory bread, Arabic bread, Tanour bread and microwave bread, in addition to the comparison group that was fed casein as a protein source) was (1.419, 1.183, 1.377, 1.708 , 1.254 ,and 1.820) respectively. It was 2.939 for the comparison group. These differences were not significant. However, it was found that the Arabic bread was superior in its nutritional value and decreased in stone bread. It was found that there is a linear relationship between the percentage of lysine in the types of bread that were estimated by the chemical method (TNBS) and the PER of those types that were estimated by the biological method, where the correlation coefficient was $r = 0.91$.

Keywords: *bread, baking process, lysine, nutritional value.*

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Introduction

Wheat is considered one of the most important economic crops in the world, covering 23.4% of global food needs. It is also a food source for approximately 40% of the world's population and provides 20% of calories and protein in the human diet (Mashhour Nawaf, 2007; Bakk and Vickersm, 2017).

A loaf of bread is the basic element in the diet of all people, so it is considered one of the main and important foods for individuals and peoples.

It is primarily based on wheat, which is still one of the most important and widely used grains in Iraqi diets, it represents 75% of the consumed grains. The amount of bread consumed per person per day in developing countries ranges between 137-411 grams (Saleh et al., 2014; Sexena & Haridas, 2004).

Global consumption of bread has increased significantly in recent years, following major scientific developments in the bread industry. Despite the importance of wheat as a protein source, its proteins are considered incomplete due to a deficiency in the amino acid, primarily,

and threonine and tryptophan, secondarily (Ali et al., 2022).

These are essential amino acids necessary for the growth and renewal of body cells. The process of converting wheat grains into flour also causes the loss of some of these acids. Due to the removal of a large portion of the bran, especially from the aleurone layer and the germ, which contain a high percentage of proteins and amino acids. Also, the flour manufacturing process causes the loss of some important nutrients such as dietary fiber, antioxidant compounds, some vitamins and minerals (Saccotelli et al., 2017; Alan et al., 2012).

The baking process also causes a significant loss in the percentage of Essential amino acids, especially lysine acid, and the loss was greater in the crust than in the (Crumb), as a result of the interaction of lysine with reducing sugars, called brown reactions (Meillard reaction). These reactions convert amino acids from acids ready for absorption into bound acids, not available for absorption and utilization (Fitzgerald et al., 2014; Srey et al., 2010; Almoraie & Israa, 2021; Sluimer, 2005).

Materials and Methods

French Bread

It was obtained Private sector ovens (Local markets). After the samples were brought, crust was separated from the Crumb, then dried separately in an air oven at (37-40)°C for 24 hours. The dried samples were crushed by a hand mortar, each for the, crust, Crumb, and whole loaf(bread) separately, then ground in a (Brabender) (Whily mill) to smooth the samples. They were stored in polyethylene bags at (-17)°C until use.

Local Loaf (Bread)

Obtained from local markets baking process at 400-450°C for one minute. The loaf was cooled for 12-15 minutes, dried, ground, and stored in polyethylene bags.

Tannour Bread

Produced in an oil oven: at a temperature between 310-400°C for (1) minute.

Stone Bread

Obtained from a private bakery and baked at 400-450°C for three minutes. The crust was separated from the, Crumb, and the same processes as above were performed (dried, ground, and stored in polyethylene bags).

Laboratory Bread

It was manufactured according to the standard method (14 AACC (10-10)). The samples were baked in an electric oven at 225°C for 17-20 minutes. The crust was separated from the crumb, and the same processes as above were performed. (dried, ground, and stored in polyethylene bags).

Bread a Microwave Oven

It was manufactured according to the standard method (14 AACC (10-10)), except for the use of a microwave oven (Microwave Oven NE-15/0) produced by the National Company to prepare it at a power of (1500) watts for 1.5 minutes.

Vitamin-Free Casein was used as a comparison source for the nutritional value of proteins. It was given to the standard group of rats and, it was obtained from the company (ICN).

Chemical Tests

Moisture, ash, and protein content were estimated (using the constant factor (NX 5.7)) according to the standard method (AACC 19 (0.8-0.1)), while the fat content was estimated using (Goldfish extract) and using the solvent (diethyl ether) according to the approved standard method (A.A.C.C. (2003) 44-16), and the lysine available for the samples was estimated according to the standard method A.O.A.C. (2005) using trinitrobenzene sulfonic acid (TNBS).

Animal Experiments

These animals were divided into six groups (1, 2, 3, 3, 4, 5, 6), with four animals per group. Each group was weighed and fed a type of bread as 10% protein source. The control group was also fed a complete diet containing other nutrients (casein). The animals and their food intake were weighed every three days, with drinking water replaced twice a week. The experiment lasted for

28 days. The feed efficiency ratio (FER) and protein efficiency ratio (PER) were calculated for each group.

The variance analysis for the factorial experiments was performed according to a completely randomized design, and the significance of the means was tested using the least significant difference (LSD) test and Duncan's test .

Results and Discussion

The results of Table 1 showed no significant differences in the moisture content of the bread types (electric bread, stone bread, laboratory bread, local bread, tandoor bread, and microwave bread). The moisture content ranged between 11.40 and 12.6%, and these percentages were close due to the bread being dried and stored under the same conditions of temperature and time. The results of the same table also indicate that the protein content of the bread types studied was close, with the highest percentage being in the Arabic loaf (12.68%) and the lowest in the tandoor loaf (10.76%).

It is noted from the same table that there are no significant differences between the fat percentages of these types except for the laboratory bread, where the fat percentage was significantly high due to the addition of fat at a rate of 2.5% during its manufacturing method.

As for the ash percentages, it was found that there were no significant differences between these percentages and they ranged between (0.55-0.92 %). The carbohydrate percentage was also calculated by the difference, which ranged between (73.07-74.85%), and there were no significant differences between the types of bread studied.

These percentages were consistent with the results of (Jalal Ahmed Fadl and others 2010) and (Jassim Mohaisen Naser and others 2013) and close to the results of (Tahani Al-Ayed and Mitham Jalis 2022) and (Abdul Hamid Bajash Abdullah and others 2016) and (Ibtisam Abdul Hamid Saleh and others.(2012)

Table 1. Chemical Composition of the Types of Bread Used in the Study

bread types	Moisture%	Protine%	Fat%	Ash%	Carbohydred %
French bread	12.60	10.72	1.50	0.60	74.58
Stone bread	12.27	11.19	1.47	0.88	74.64
Laboratory bread	11.51	11.20	2.06	0.92	74.32
Local loaf	11.40	12.68	1.52	0.55	73.85
Tannour bread	11.90	10.76	1.41	0.86	73.07
L.S.D 0.05	0.48	0.49	0.38	0.38	2.69

As for the content of the amino acid lysine in local bread types and the percentage of loss during the baking process, the results of Table (2) indicate that the lysine values in flour and the types of bread studied (Franch bread, stone bread, laboratory bread, local loaf, oven loaf and microwave bread) were (2.946, 2.884, 2.762, 2.920, 2.860, 2.946) for flour, respectively. We did not observe significant differences in the lysine percentages in the types of bread, as they were (2.718, 2.430, 2.538, 2.853, 2.510 and 3.102%) for bread, respectively. These percentages were lower than what was obtained by Rehab Farouk Mohammed Ali1.(2022)

Microwave bread was distinguished by its lysine content, while its percentage was lower in stone bread compared to other types.

Lysine loss rates varied among the bread types studied, ranging from 7.739% , 15.742%, 8.11%, 2.31%, 12.23% and 0%, respectively.

A slight variation in lysine loss rates was observed between French and laboratory- bread, ranging from 7.739% to 8.11%, respectively.

A greater loss of lysine was observed in stone bread (15.742%). This may be due to the baking conditions and the increased thickness and color of the crust layer. Brown color is closely related to increased lysine loss due to the presence of

reducing sugars and free amino acids, especially lysine, which leads to the formation or occurrence of a series of non-enzymatic chemical reactions. The combination of these reactions is known as the Maillard reaction, and these reactions lead to the formation of the distinctive brown color of the bread crust as well as the special flavor of the bread.

This was confirmed by Yanting Shen et al. (2018), Nicholas Palamidis's, P. Markakis's (2007), and Patel et al. (2019). From the same table, it was noted that the percentage of lysine loss in the tandoor loaf was higher than that in the local loaf (12.23 and 2.31%), respectively.

The reason for not getting a dark brown colour in local bread may be attributed to the short duration of the baking process used. This fact is consistent with the results of Markakis, P. (1980) and Wang H-Y et al. (2011).

No loss of lysine was observed in microwaved bread. It was shown from the same table and figure (1) that the loss of lysine is greater in the crust than in the crumb for the types of bread studied, and when calculating the percentage of difference in the loss of lysine between the crust and the crumb in the types of bread studied, it was noted that the difference in the percentage

of lysine between the crust and the crumb in the types of bread (electric, stone, laboratory and microwave bread) was (7.8, 11.75, 8.5 and 0% respectively), and the stone bread was distinguished by a high percentage of loss between the crust and the crumbs, and the reason may be attributed to the conditions of the baking process in terms of temperature and time, which was reflected in the increase in the thickness of the crust layer with an increase in its color as a result of the Miller reactions between sugars and amino acids, especially lysine acid. This was also confirmed by (Tajammal Hussain et al., 2004) and (Yanting Shen et al., 2018).

The same table also showed that there was no loss in the percentage of this acid in the crust and crumb of microwaved bread, because of the baking process in this method does not produce a brown crust.

But a very slight increase in lysine acid was noted. This may be attributed to the additives added to the flour when preparing bread, such as yeast. It was also found that there is a direct relationship between the intensity of the brown color in bread types and the loss of lysine. This was confirmed by (Wang, Qian, & Yao, 2011).

Table 2. Effect of Baking Conditions on the Loss of Lysine in Bread Types (g/100g Protein)

Bread type	Lysine in bread%	Lysine in flour%	The percentage of lysine loss between the crust and the crumb%	Lysine loss%
French bread	2.718	2.946		7.739
crust	2.599		7.8	11.77
crumb	2.818			4.344
Stone bread	2.430	2.884		15.742
Crust	2.252		11.75	21.91
crumb	2.652			8.044
Laboratory bread	2.538	2.762		8.11
crust	2.422		8.5	12.30
crumb	2.651			4.96
Local loaf	2.853	2.920		2.31
Tandoor bread	2.510	2.860		12.23
Microwave bread	3.102	2.946	0	No loss

Table (3) shows that the Food Efficiency Ratio (FER) consumed by groups of mice (1; 2: 3: 4; 5; 6) that were fed the studied bread types in addition to the comparison group, (French bread, stone bread, laboratory bread, local loaf,

tandoor bread, microwave loaf and (casein)) as protein sources were (17.02, 15.01, 16.35, 19.32, 16.27, 19.41% and 39.26%) ,, respectively. There were slight and insignificant differences between them.

Figure 1. Shows the Percentage of Lysine Loss in the Crust and Crumb of the Studied Types of Bread

With the exception of the value of the (FER) of the comparison group 1, as high, because the

protein source was casin, and this was reflected in the rate of the weight of the laboratory animals for the types of bread under the study.

It was noted that the comparison group which fed casein was characterized by a high increase in the average weight of the animals, (98.760) grams, The reason is due to the quality of the good protein in the food of this group,

As for the groups of animals that consumed the studied types of bread as a protein source, their weight ranged between (31.15) grams for the stone bread group to (39.30) grams for the microwave loaf group during the experimental period (28 days), and there were no statistically significant differences in the weight gain of the animals for the groups of studied bread types. This was reflected in the Food Efficiency Ratio (FER), and protein efficiency ratio (PER) for the types of bread.

Table 3. Shows the Average Food Intake, Weight Gain of Rats, and Feed Efficiency Ratio (FER) for the Types of Bread Studied for a Period of 28 Days

Group number	Protein source	Feed intake (g)	Weight gain (g)	Food Efficiency Value (FER)
1	Casein	249.112a	98.760a	A39.26
2	French bread	b209.470	35.32 b	b17.02
3	Stone bread	207.420b	31.15 b	b15.01
4	Laboratory bread	196,750 b	32.17 b	b16.35
5	Local loaf	195.420b	37.77 b	b19.32
6	Tannour bread	192.350b	31.30 b	b16.27
7	Microwave bread	202.421b	39.30 b	19.41 b

Table (4) shows that the amounts of protein consumed by groups (1,2,3,4,5,6) over 28 days had slight differences, but they were not significant, and were much less than the amount of protein consumed by the comparison group containing casein

where the difference was significant, and this is due to the good quality of protein represented by casein. Therefore, the PER value of casein (2.939) was significantly higher than the PER values of other types of bread, while the PER of bread types was generally low, ranging from 1.183 for the stone bread group to 1.820 for the microwave loaf group.

It was also noted that the PER value of the local loaf (1.708) was close to the PER value of the

microwave loaf (1.820), and the reason may be due to the lack of brown color in the two types of bread (Arafah et al, 1980; Faridi, et al. 1982).

The same table (4) showed The PER values for French bread and laboratory bread were (1.419 and 1.377) respectively, and they were also close, as the baking process conditions were almost similar for both types.

Stone bread and tenor (oven) bread recorded the lowest PER values due to the harshness of the baking process conditions in terms of temperature and time, and this was reflected in the increase in the intensity of the brown color, which negatively affected the percentage of lysine loss in them, as this was reflected in the value of protein efficiency for them. There is a

strong linear relationship between the lysine content of bread and the PER, represented by a correlation coefficient of ($r = 90$), and Figure (2) also illustrates this relationship.

This was also confirmed by (Tajammal Hussain et al. 2005), through their studies on lysine fortification of wheat flour to improve the

nutritional status in Pakistan, and also (Al-Nouri, F.F. 1961) in his study on the nutritional value of wheat and bulgur proteins, and (Tsen, C.C. et al. 1982) through their studies on the effect of microwave and steam baking on the nutritional value of bread.

Table 4. Shows the Protein Intake, Weight Gain of Mice, and the Protein Value (PER) for the Studied Species

Group no.	rotein source	Amount of protein consumed (g)	Weight gain (g)	Protein efficiency ratio (PER)
1	Casein	30.210a	88.810 a	2.939 a
2	French bread	17.05 b	24.21 b	1.419 b
3	Stone bread	17.905 b	21.190 b	1.183 b
4	Laboratory bread	18.169b	25.03 b	1.377 b
5	Local loaf	17.422b	29.77 b	1.708 b
6	Tannour bread	17.780 b	22.310 b	1.254 b
7	Microwave bread	17.1200 b	29.821 b	1.820 b

Note: a, b, c The same letter indicates no significant differences according to Duncan's test at the 0.05 level.

Figure 2. Shows the Relationship between the Available Lysine in the Studied Types of Bread and the Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER)

Note: $PER = \text{Gain in body mass(g)} / \{\text{Protein intake(g)}\}$

Conclusion

This research yielded a set of positive results that contribute to a scientific understanding of the research topic within its scientific framework. These results also demonstrated the importance of the studied variables and their role in explaining the phenomenon under investigation.

The implications of these results are not limited to the scope of this study alone, but extend to broader scientific and applied fields, thus enhancing their theoretical and practical value. We aspire for these research findings to open new horizons for researchers and specialists in this field to study the topic more broadly and from multiple perspectives, including expanding

the sample size or employing other research methodologies and analytical tools. Furthermore, these results raise a number of open research questions not addressed in this study, forming a foundation for future work that contributes to the development of knowledge in this field, paving the way for future research directions and moving beyond unjustified speculation, while supporting and applying these results in a sound scientific manner.

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